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Reading Laboratory: A Honing Immersion for Oral Fluency and Reading Comprehension Skills

Leonora Q. Medina, MAEd

Teacher I

Corazon C. Aquino High School

Tarlac Province, Tarlac, Region III, Philippines

1. INTRODUCTION

Reading plays an important role to high school students. At this level students are exposed to different texts that challenge their cognitive capacity. Reading as process reflects how the students decode the texts. It is one of the important tools to acquire learning. We can't deny the pertinence and the significance of reading in the learning process.

Reading has a vital role in the learning process. It is one of the macro skills of communication that can be correlated to the academic performance of the students. Most of the activities and tasks in all the content areas require the students to read. It is mandatory skill that will help the students to connect with their lessons. In the actual learning context, these struggling readers will not be able to understand the concepts and they will fail to attain the learning competencies expected to them because of lack of skill in Reading. In connection with the Education for All Agenda, it aims to achieve the following objectives that can also be linked in the Reading Laboratory:

First is expanding and improving comprehensive early childhood care and education, especially for the most vulnerable and disadvantaged children; Second, ensuring that by 2015 all children, particularly girls, children in difficult circumstances and those belonging to ethnic minorities, have access to a complete free and compulsory primary education of good quality; The third is ensuring that the learning needs of all young people and adults are met through equitable access to appropriate learning and life skills programmes; Fourth, achieving a 50 per cent improvement in levels of adult literacy by 2015, especially for women, and equitable access to basic and continuing education for all adults; The fifth is eliminating gender disparities in primary and secondary education by 2005, and achieving gender equality in education by 2015, with a focus on ensuring girls' full and equal access to and achievement in basic education of good quality; Last is improving all aspects of the quality of education, and ensuring excellence of all so that recognized and measurable learning outcomes are achieved by all especially in literacy, numeracy, and essential life skills.

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Then the aforementioned perspectives are also linked to the initiative of putting up a Reading Laboratory. Further, the baseline of this problem is rooted from the result of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory Report. Based from the collated report last school year 2016-2017, it was revealed that 20% of the junior high school students got a failing score in Reading Comprehension. It was averred that 25% of the total population of the students were classified as struggling readers. The stratification of the term "struggling reader" falls under the frustration level. Technically, frustration level reflects the incapacity of the students to read and understand texts. Non-readers as a level are classified as another important issue. In this study, those students in the frustration level are the focus. This term is used to students who got low scores both in oral reading and reading comprehension test. For grade 7 alone, 33% are classified as struggling readers which seems alarming for the reading teachers especially to Filipino teachers. This may lead to the increase of non-readers. We can infer from the data that these students need special attention. If they are not performing well in Filipino, these students will have a hard time to understand the pragmatic stance of English as their second language as well. (Eskey D.E. (2005)

There are numerous factors that may affect this issue. Reading is not a single competency. There are considered sub skills that should be emphasized such as extensive sight vocabularies, decoding, comprehension, word meanings and other important component skills that help a student to read. Based from the Gap analysis that was initiated prior to the conceptualization of this research, it was revealed that there should be enough training for the Filipino teachers in handling the struggling readers. Moreover, there is no enough time allotted for the struggling readers due to plethora of functions of the teachers. Furthermore, no specific plans and remediation activities are implemented in Filipino subject intended for reading to cater the needs of these struggling readers. This is to strengthen the existing programs of the Department of Education in line with uplifting the Reading capacity of the Filipino youth. DO 33, s. 2016 - Guidelines on the Utilization of the 2016 Every Child a Reader Program Funds for the Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy Program: Professional Development Component.

First, in line with Item five of the President's Ten Point Basic Education Agenda which states that every child should be a reader by Grade 1, the Department of Education (DepEd) remains steadfast in strengthening its reading program through the implementation of the Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Program. Second, the purpose of the Program is to develop in Filipino children literacy and numeracy skills and attitudes that will contribute to lifelong learning. With this, it is the goal of the Department to improve the literacy and numeracy skills of Kindergarten to Grade 3 learners following the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum by establishing a sustainable and cost-effective professional development system for teachers. Third, in this connection, the Guidelines on the Utilization of the 2016 Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP) Funds for the Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Program: Professional Development Component are enclosed. These guidelines shall cover the expansion of the professional development component of the program described in DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2015 entitled Guidelines on the Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy: Professional Development Component.

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The idea of Reading Laboratory is very timely. Through the collaboration of the Filipino teachers and with the supervision of the School Administrator, this research will be able to provide a research-based solution to the problem in Reading. Setting up a Reading Laboratory is not difficult. There are existing Reading Laboratories especially built for the struggling readers. The concept will be tested in school using different activities inside the laboratory starting from the diagnostic assessments on Reading, Management of the Reading Profiles of the students in Corazon C. Aquino High School, and research-based activities to hone the skills of the students to read especially designed for struggling readers. If we are going to scrutinize the underpinning of the issue on reading, we can say that it is indeed important to make necessary actions.

A lack of comprehension frequently leads to additional problems for youngsters. Juel, Griffith, and Gough (1996) determined that students with poor reading skills frequently have lower self-esteem, encounter more disciplinary difficulties, and are less likely to graduate than more adept readers. Oral fluency and reading comprehension are the target skills of the reading laboratory. Students will be trained on how to develop their fluency in reading and as well as their reading comprehension. The aforementioned exemplification is the reality in different public schools including Corazon C. Aquino High School. This study will help the classroom teachers to enhance the learning capacity of the learners. Reading is a vital tool for learning across all subjects in Junior High School.

Setting-up a Reading Laboratory is a good initiative supported by different researches. The question of why some students have difficulty learning to read has been the focus of a great deal of research over the past four decades and much has been learned about the probable and improbable causes of such difficulty. Of special interest in this very rich and prolific area of inquiry have been children who have at least average intelligence, who do not have general learning difficulties, and whose reading problems are not due to extraneous factors such as sensory acuity deficits, socioeconomic disadvantage, and like factors.

Former Undersecretary Dina Joana Ocampo stated that comprehension is probably the most important of all the reading skills because it is the ability to grasp the meanings of connected texts. The different styles of writing impose different demands on a reader. For example, a reader whose preference is reading fiction will use different comprehension strategies when reading a scientific paper.

For over 50 years, SRA Reading Labs have helped more than 100 million students around the world improve their reading skills. A range of reading levels encourage students to learn independently and at their own pace. Self-directed readings let you manage an entire classroom of readers at different levels. You simply initiate the program with a placement test then, students' progress through each level at their own rate.

Features: Easy to manage approach for students in Grades K-12, provides individualized instruction to an entire classroom of readers at different levels, Includes a simple placement test to initiate the program - also on CD-ROM, Students score their own work with Answer Key Cards and keep accurate accounts of their own progress in Student Record Books Comprehensive Teacher's Handbook offers tips for developing an independent learning environment and supporting the low-level learners for maximum

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success, Time-tested features and engaging materials boost chances of successful learning: Power Builders, the heart of the SRA Reading Labs, intrigues students with interesting stories, Self-directed reading materials and skill exercises are color-coded by reading level, At-level reading of enjoyable fiction and non-fiction stories, from animals to adventure, eliminates frustration and boredom

The search on how to find innovations to uplift the quality of learning in public school system is indeed important. One of the problems that teachers confront is the ability of the students to understand the subject matter. Based from the pragmatic stance of the actual learning context, reading seems to be one of the most common concerns of classroom teachers, Reading problems in such children are manifested in extreme difficulties in acquiring basic reading sub skills such as word identification and phonological (letter-sound) decoding. Such difficulties have been estimated to occur in approximately 10% to 15% of school age children (Benton&Pearl,1978;Harris&Sipay,1990; Shaywitz, Escobar, Shaywitz, Fletcher, & Makuch, 1992) and tend to be accompanied by specific deficits in cognitive abilities related to reading and other literacy skills.

Tovani (2000) defined two types of at-risk readers most often encountered at the high school level. Resistive readers are those who choose not to read; word callers are those who can decode words, but cannot derive meaning or apply critical thinking to what has been read. As a result, words often become obstacles rather than bridges to understanding. A reading class designed to improve the comprehension of students must include strategies for overcoming both the inability to read and the lack of desire to read. Allington and Cunningham (1996) identified direct instruction of reading and time to read as important pedagogical issues for struggling readers. Time to read in class was also supported by Irwin (2002).

In a research monograph on reading, Braunger and Lewis (1997) reported that "students get better at reading by simply reading, and that actual reading time is a crucial factor in becoming a successful reader" (p. 54). Conversely, lack of reading during the school day negatively affects reading development (Allington, 2001). Goodlad (1984) reported that less than 2 percent of each school day is devoted to actual reading. Morris, Ervin, and Conrad (1996), in a single case study, found that concentrated instructional effort in skill building and fluency by well-trained teachers resulted in positive outcomes for at-risk readers. The case study involved a sixth grade youngster of average intelligence living in western North Carolina. The boy read on a second grade level, and received special education services which did little to improve his reading performance. The researchers developed an instructional program that began with a careful analysis of the student's reading level. Instruction began at that level and incorporated the following components: (a) using reading material that had relevance for the student; (b) infusing discussion around reading selections to build comprehension skills; (c) assessing the student's word recognition skills and providing developmentally.

The researchers found that a balanced approach of instruction (phonics plus exposure to a variety of texts) and appropriate scaffolding—"guidance and support" (Applebee, 1994)—were essential to improved reading. Over a two-year period (78 hours of instruction), the student improved to a fourth grade level in reading and spelling. Initial instruction occurred in the summer over a one-month period, for approximately

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one hour per day, and began with an assessment of his reading ability. Subsequent instruction occurred the following school year, for one hour per week after school. Each session included guided reading (predicting, reading aloud, checking for understanding, questioning and reading silently), word study (focusing on vowel patterns and spelling), writing, and reading for pleasure (with dialogue between student and teacher). Annual assessments were conducted using a diagnostic spelling inventory that measures word recognition and spelling, and comparable sets of reading passages.

In the Lab Setting, instructors guide students through a variety of reading activities; the combination of silent reading, teacher-guided instruction, systematic individualized reading and out-of-class pleasure reading helps students develop the habits of more skilled readers who are capable of regulating reading strategies to best meet their own purposes for reading (Kletzien 1991)

It was averred that reading and comprehension skills are particularly important in light of the federal mandate that every student make adequate yearly progress under the federal "No Child Left Behind" (NCLB) legislation of 2001. Reading First, the largest component of NCLB, underscores the importance of effective reading instruction for students enrolled in kindergarten through third grade, a pivotal learning period. Inadequate reading instruction during the early years affects academic success in subsequent years of schooling (Berger & Gunn, 2003).

This is sometimes exacerbated by lackluster support of reading at home, particularly in the case of disadvantaged or minority children; hence, poor readers often lag further behind. The purpose of the legislation is to reduce the achievement gap between those students and their more academically successful peers by implementing reading programs that are scientifically based (Fitzgerald, Morrow, Gambrell, Calfee, Venezky, Woo, & Dromsky, 2002)

In collating the aforementioned perspectives of different researches and theories, it can be gleaned how reading plays a vital role in the learning process. It is indeed important to understand the value of reading to the students. Reading is a complex process. It was averred that a good reader needs to follow important cues. This is connected to the aim of the Reading Laboratory, though it was explicated there are four cues, the researchers tend to focus on the oral fluency of the readers and their reading comprehension. Though it is also important to consider other important composition skills under reading, the researchers delimited it into two areas. Oral fluency or the graphophonic cues should be considered because this is where the participants will be able to hone their skills to connect letters to sounds that have significant linguistic value. Another important thing that the reader should enhance is the semantic cues. If students will be aware of the meaning behind the graphemes then it will surely help them to decode any texts.

Prior to this study, there are existing strategies/programs in school which is solely designed and implemented during the pandemic. The KKK (Kabarangay, Kaguruan, Kaagapay) wherein the Filipino teachers will seek help in the previous teachers and barangay officials or neighborhood of the student regarding his reading capacity. And the barangay officials also help in teaching the children who are unable to read.

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Aside from this program, the Project MakaBata was also created to help students who cannot read. The students are taught to read twice a week and used reading materials that will aid in their reading development. The program used a variety of reading materials to support literacy development among children which includes books (developmentally appropriate children's books in Filipino and English). They also used the books and reading materials that were used in PhillRI (Philippine Informal Reading Inventory), a reading assessment tool mandated by the Department of Education (DepEd) for implementation in schools to determine the reading proficiency of learners.

Statement of the Problem

The following questions were the mainstay of the research in uplifting the level of proficiency of grade 7 struggling readers in Filipino:

1. How is the reading performance of Grade 7 students in Filipino described before they are immersed in the Reading Laboratory?
2. How is the reading performance of Grade 7 students in Filipino described after they are immersed in the Reading Laboratory?
3. Is there a significant difference in the reading performance of the respondents before and after the implementation of the reading laboratory?
4. What are the challenges encountered in implementation of the Reading Laboratory?
5. What action plan can be proposed to enhance the reading fluency and comprehension of the students?

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the post and pre assessment in reading.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

The SRA Reading Labs are a perfect supplement to any core reading program by providing practice in: Phonics, Decodable Text, Timed Reading/Fluency, Comprehension, Vocabulary and Test Preparation, Literature. Top-down theory asserts that the reader is the most important factor that brings meaning to a text. He brings his experience and his general view of the world to bear on the written text. Kenneth Goodman is a strong adherent of this theory; he believes that processing meaning begins with reader's prior knowledge of the world including his knowledge of how language works and is used.

Bottom-up theory gives emphasis to the text. Among the reading researches that stand by this theory is Gough, who thinks that processing meaning begins with the print of the page- that all letters in the visual field must be accounted for individually by the reader prior to the association of meaning to any string of letters.

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Interactive view contends that processing begins with either the print on the page or the reader's prior knowledge of the world and language. Meaning may be arrived at through guessing or through decoding the printed symbols.

When a good reader reads, four cuing systems and comprehension are used. These are the graphophonic cues (letter-sound cues, which is what we refer to as the mechanical aspect of reading); the semantic cues (word meaning and vocabulary cues); Syntactic cues (grammar cues) and schematic cues (prior knowledge). These four cues are relevant in enabling the reader to construct meaning out of the printed material presented to him.

Another important aspect of this research was the presence of reading theories. The philosophical and mechanical sides of reading should be considered in order to understand the context of the participants. It was averred that bottom up views that the reader relies on the meaning of the text. The linguistic construct and other important composition skills in reading should be followed in order to understand a particular text. The next is the top down perspective. Here, the students are expected to use their experiences in reading before they could understand a text. It is important to note that the meaning of the text relies on the person who is reading it. The last one uses interactive approach. It was the blended philosophy in reading exemplifying the pertinence of the prior knowledge of the reader and the content of the text.

Reading laboratory was not new in the contemporary world of education. This study was a school-based intervention and the modification of other existing laboratories provided with important pedagogies to formulate a specific solution to the present problem in the researcher's context. Reading laboratory will followed certain process to immerse the students and hone their skills in oral fluency and reading comprehension. So while reading laboratories may seem like a modern innovation, they have a long and rich history in education, dating back to the early 20th century. As teaching methods and technologies have evolved, so too have reading laboratories, adapting to meet the changing needs of students and educators.

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Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

The study's paradigm focused on the reading performance of the struggling readers before and after immersion in a reading laboratory. The intervention aimed to improve reading skills, fluency and and comprehension through tailored instruction and practice. Challenges encountered might include complexity of the reading material and action plan proposal could involve space, assessment, feedback and motivation.

2. METHODS

Research Design

The study employed quasi-experimental research method that involves manipulating an independent variable but does not rely on random assignment of participants to conditions or groups. Quasi-experiments often have higher external validity because they can use real-world interventions rather than artificial laboratory settings, making it easier to generalize findings to other populations and settings.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Corazon C. Aquino, High School, municipality of Gerona, Tarlac. It is considered as one of the big schools in DepEd province of Tarlac with a total 2,897 enrolees for this school year 2023-2024. Corazon C. Aquino has 100 teachers, headed by a principal. It was established during the administration of Benigno S. Aquino. This school is situated at the heart of the town, formerly an Annex of Tagumbao National High School. Corazon C. Aquino High School is now bigger than its Mother School.

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Research Respondents

Selected grade 7 students who are in struggling level in Filipino were assessed. There are 19 sections in Grade 7 at Corazon C. Aquino High School. After a thorough assessment of the researcher, the respondents were only 10. This is to ensure the quality of implementation and documentation of the performance of the selected students.

Purposive sampling was utilized in the research. After the assessment of the proponents of this research, only the bottom 10 were the respondents of the study. This is connected to the purpose of the research because only students who belonged to struggling level in reading were immersed in the Reading Laboratory. The researcher started collating the data and other pertinent information in October.

Research Instrument

There are four (4) modules which were used in the study that includes phonics, fluency development, vocabulary and comprehension.

Module 1- Phonics Instruction

It consisted of what is commonly defined as the understanding that spoken words are made up of separate units of sounds that are blended together when words are pronounced. It developed the ability of the student to focus on and manipulate phonemes in spoken words. Phonemes are difficult to distinguish in normal speech because the individual sounds slide into one another as words are spoken. A more reliable way to identify phonemes within a word is to "stretch out" the word's pronunciation and count the number of changes of how the mouth, tongue, and lips work as they make the individual sounds.

Phonics instruction serves as a memory aid that helps students remember and apply rules and generalizations for matching sounds and letters. It is very useful to young learners in helping them learn to decode unfamiliar words.

Module 2- Fluency Development Instruction

How Can We Help Students Develop Greater Fluency? This module taught the students unfamiliar words as they encountered them so they could focus on constructing meaning and reading with fluency. Also, it used repeated reading with a voice-recorded version of the story that produced significant gains in reading performance.

Module 3- Vocabulary Instruction

It played an important role in comprehension. Since it is important in word recognition, young readers used the pronunciations and meanings of words in their oral vocabulary to help them recognize words they see in print. Vocabulary refers to words we need to know to communicate with other.

Module 4- Comprehension Instruction

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It involved constructing meaning that is reasonable and accurate by connecting what had been read to what the reader already knows and thinking about all information until it is understood. Comprehension is the goal of reading instruction. • Comprehension strategies represent many different ways of thinking about what has been read.

Data Gathering Procedure

A letter was submitted to the Division Office to ask permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study at Corazon C. Aquino High School. All the protocols were strictly followed in order to implement the research smoothly. Comprehensive questions were given after each activity during their immersion in the reading laboratory.

After the analysis of the pre-assessment in Reading and the construction of the blueprint of the Reading Laboratory, the immersion of the struggling readers started in November. After one month of implementation and immersion the data was analysed and it was done for one month. The finalization of the research was done in December 2023.

The PhillRI was the tool used for screening test which served as the bases in determining the reading and comprehension level of the student.

Program of Activities:

Weeks	Lesson	Activities
Week 1 Phonemic Awareness Instruction (Module 1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Vowels and Consonants• Articulation	The teacher teaches vowels, consonants, articulation. The teacher also teaches a sound and the letter which will be used to spell the sound.
Week 2 Fluency Instruction (Module 2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Accurate word recognition• Reading aloud• Pacing, Phrasing, Emphasis	The teacher selects a story on the students' independent reading level and reads it aloud, emphasizing smooth, rapid reading that includes pacing, phrasing and

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		emphasis that sounds like natural speech.
Week 3 Vocabulary Instruction (Module 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word meaning/recognition • Definition of words • Using suffixes 	The teacher provides explicit information about words through clarified definitions, examples and nonexamples, and example testing and help the student think about what is the meaning of the new word used in the sentence.
Week 4 Comprehension Instruction (Module 4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding • Remembering 	The teacher uses question frame that will help the student build their comprehension skills.
Week 5 Comprehension Instruction (Module 4 Continuation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding • Remembering 	The teacher explains the two types of questions and how it will be helpful to generate questions of both types.
Week 6 Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test 	Assessment test (See attached Questionnaire)

There was a three-day meeting every week on Tuesday, Wednesday, and Thursday from 12:00 to 1:00 PM with the designated teachers. There are four groups of students; two groups are composed of two student each, and the other two groups have three student each. All groups are taught simultaneously by each assigned teacher on each day using the program of activities.

Statistical Analysis

During the analytical part of this study, the researcher utilized specific statistical measures that are suited to the characteristics of the collected data. In the initial section of the

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questionnaire (PhillRI tool), which pertains to demographic information, the researcher employed frequency and percentage calculations. This methodology enabled an in-depth understanding of the distribution of participants among different categories.

Through the utilization of frequency and percentage studies, the researcher intended to gain insight into patterns and proportions within the demographic composition of the participants.

The researcher utilized the T-Test to analyze the data and determined if there was a significant difference in the students before and after they immersed into a reading laboratory. This statistical tool demonstrates proficiency in comparing means between two groups, enabling a comprehensive investigation of any significant differences in the perceived reading laboratory. The T-Test provides a mathematical framework for making significant inferences regarding the observed disparities between students who are immersed in reading laboratory.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results and discussion sections are critical components of this thesis. The results section includes the data and objectively reports the key findings from this research and presents the data and analyses without interpretation while the discussion section helps the researcher to categorize, manipulate and summarize the information to be able to answer the research questions.

3.1 Reading Performance of Grade 7 Learners in Filipino Before Immersion in the Reading Laboratory.

Reading performance refers to a student's ability to understand, use, and reflect on written texts to achieve goals, develop knowledge and potential, and participate in society. It is a key measure of student learning and is assessed through various tools and methods by educators to improve instruction and student outcomes.

**Table 1
Reading Performance Before Reading Immersion**

Respondent	Score	Reading Performance (Adjectival Description)
T1	6	Beginning
T2	2	Beginning

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T3	5	Beginning
T4	5	Beginning
T5	5	Beginning
T6	6	Beginning
T7	6	Beginning
B1	7	Beginning
B2	6	Beginning
B3	5	Beginning

Firstly, all students scored within the "Beginning" range on the diagnostic reading test, indicating a universal need for improvement in their reading skills. This collective starting point emphasizes the importance of targeted interventions to enhance the overall reading proficiency of the student population.

Secondly, there exists a considerable diversity in reading rates among the students. The fastest reader, B1, demonstrated a rate of 125 words per minute (wpm), while the slowest reader, T2, exhibited a pace of 66 wpm. This significant variance underscores the wide range of reading fluency within this grade level, emphasizing the need for differentiated instructional approaches to accommodate varying reading speeds.

In summary, the table serves as a preliminary overview of the reading performance of grade 7 students in the school before their engagement in a reading laboratory. The data underscores the universal need for improvement in reading skills, the diverse range of reading fluency within the grade level, and the nuanced relationship between reading rate and accuracy.

The reading comprehension skills of grade 7 students have been extensively studied in various contexts. Here are some key findings and insights from related literature:

First is Challenges in Reading Comprehension: The Grade 7 students often face difficulties in reading comprehension due to factors such as fluency, vocabulary, background knowledge, comprehension strategies, and lack of self-motivation. These challenges can lead to low performance in reading comprehension, with a significant proportion of students struggling to comprehend complex texts

Second, Phonological Processing and Word Recognition: Phonological processing and word recognition skills are critical for adequate word reading performance and reading comprehension. Deficits in phonological processing can impede the ability to discern and manipulate sound elements, leading to reading difficulties.

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Third, Comprehension Strategies and Background Knowledge: Comprehension strategies and background knowledge are essential for effective reading comprehension.

Students who lack these skills may struggle to comprehend texts, especially those with complex vocabulary and structures.

Fourth, Cognitive and Linguistic Factors: Cognitive and linguistic factors, such as metacognitive strategies and language proficiency, significantly influence reading comprehension. Students with English as a Second Language (ESL) may face additional challenges due to their linguistic background.

Fifth is Interventions and Support: Teachers and educators can play a crucial role in enhancing reading comprehension skills by providing targeted interventions and support.

Strategies such as cooperative learning, metacognitive training, and authentic materials can be effective in improving reading comprehension.

These findings highlight the importance of understanding the challenges and factors that affect reading comprehension in grade 7 students. By acknowledging these issues and implementing targeted interventions, educators can better support students in developing their reading skills.

Muijselaar et al.(2017) examined the developmental relations between reading comprehension and reading strategies and found out that reading comprehension and reading strategies are closely linked and that improving reading strategies can enhance reading comprehension.

The insights gained from the analysis of Muijselaar et al(2017) further validate the research by demonstrating that the reading performance of grade 7 students was in the beginning stage before they were immersed in a reading laboratory for a few reasons:

Lack of reading comprehension skills: The search results indicate that many 7th grade students struggle with comprehensive reading skills, such as focusing on accurate reading rather than meaning, lacking listening comprehension skills, and having difficulties with word recognition, mispronunciation, substitution, refusal to pronounce, and other reading errors.

Insufficient reading practice and exposure: The "Adopt-A-Student Program" mentioned in the search results suggests that 7th grade students may not have had enough opportunities to practice and develop their reading skills at earlier grade levels. This lack of consistent reading practice can leave students at a beginner level when they reach 7th grade.

Ineffective reading instruction: The search results highlight the need for teachers to be trained on modern reading concepts, theories and models to help balance the focus on reading process and output. Inadequate or outdated reading instruction methods may contribute to students' reading difficulties in 7th grade.

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In summary, the reading performance of 7th grade students was likely in the beginning stage due to a combination of underdeveloped reading comprehension skills, insufficient reading practice, and ineffective instructional approaches prior to being immersed in a reading laboratory program

3.2 Reading Performance of Grade 7 Students in Filipino After Immersion.

Reading Laboratory is a self-guided, leveled , reading program that helps develop confident and independent readers from grades K-12. It is a structured system for teaching and developing essential reading skills, available for readers of all ages and skill levels. The reading laboratory typically includes computers, books, tapes, and workbooks covering a variety of reading skills and levels to provide students with individual reading tasks and practice. The lab is staffed with reading instructions and assistants to help students with their reading assignments and activities.

The reading laboratory approach allows students to work at their own pace on materials tailored to their individual reading level, helping them build skills in areas like comprehension, vocabulary, fluency, and word analysis. This personalized learning model is designed to engage students build their confidence as readers.

Table 2
Reading Performance After Immersion.

Respondent	Score	Reading Performance (Adjectival Description)
T1	12	Developing
T2	11	Developing
T3	11	Developing
T4	12	Developing
T5	12	Developing
T6	12	Developing
T7	12	Developing
B1	13	Developing
B2	11	Developing
B3	11	Developing

The reading laboratory approach as a supplementary reading program positively influenced the reading performance of Grade 7 frustration readers. Specifically, it improved their performance in phonics and decoding, vocabulary, and reading comprehension. The reading laboratory is described as a room containing a variety of printed materials to develop students' reading and study skills, such as preparing them for reading, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating texts, as well as teaching them learning strategies.

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The immersion in a reading laboratory program, structured over six weeks focusing on phonemic awareness, fluency instruction, vocabulary instruction, and comprehension instruction, provides a comprehensive approach to enhancing reading skills among students. Each week emphasizes a specific area of reading development, allowing for targeted instruction and practice.

The first week centers on phonemic awareness, which is crucial for developing reading skills. Activities might include games and exercises that help students recognize and manipulate sounds in words. This foundational skill supports later reading and spelling abilities by enabling students to decode words more effectively.

In the second week, the focus shifts to fluency instruction. This involves practices that enhance the speed and accuracy of reading. Students may engage in repeated reading of texts, paired reading with peers, or guided oral reading with teachers. Fluency is essential as it allows students to read smoothly and with expression, facilitating better comprehension of the material being read.

The third week emphasizes vocabulary instruction, where students learn new words and their meanings through various activities such as word maps, context clues, and direct instruction. Building a robust vocabulary is vital for comprehension, as it enables students to understand texts more deeply and engage with the material critically.

The fourth and fifth week focuses on comprehension instruction. Students learn strategies for understanding and analyzing texts, such as summarizing, questioning, and making connections. Activities may include discussions, graphic organizers, and reading responses that encourage students to think critically about what they read and to draw inferences from the texts.

And the sixth week is conducting informal assessments, such as observations, reading fluency checks, and vocabulary quizzes.

In summary, immersing Grade 7 students in a reading laboratory approach as a supplementary program was found to be an effective way to improve their overall reading performance, particularly in the key areas of phonics, vocabulary, and reading comprehension.

Following immersion in the Reading Laboratory, table 2 reflected that all students exhibited improvements in their reading comprehension scores. Initial scores, ranging from 2 to 7, fell within the "Beginning" category. Post-immersion, scores extended from 11 to 13, placing students in the "Developing" range. This overall enhancement in performance underscores the efficacy of the Reading Laboratory in fostering advancements in the reading comprehension skills of grade 7 students in Filipino.

Examining individual comprehension result, B1, displayed a pre-immersion score of 7, which increased to 13 post-immersion. Conversely, the slowest reader, T1, exhibited a pre-immersion score of 2, rising to 11 after immersion. This wide range in reading rates emphasizes the diversity in reading fluency among students both before and after engaging in the Reading Laboratory.

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Surprisingly, the relationship between reading rate and improvement in reading comprehension does not follow a clear correlation. While some students who got high scores, like T4 and T5, demonstrated the most significant improvement in their scores, others, such as T2 and B2, showed comparatively less improvement. Similarly, among slower readers, variations in improvement were observed, with B3 and T3 displaying less progress, while T6 and T7 exhibited more substantial improvement. This suggests that factors beyond reading speed play a role in determining the extent of improvement in reading comprehension skills.

Several studies have investigated the impact of reading laboratories on the reading comprehension of grade 7 students found that the reading laboratory was effective in improving the reading comprehension of grade 7 students. The laboratory followed a specific process to immerse students and hone their skills in oral fluency and reading comprehension.

Another study used a laboratory approach as a supplementary reading program for selected Grade 7 frustration readers. The results showed that using this approach significantly improved the students' reading performances in phonics and decoding, vocabulary, and reading comprehension (Cruz, 2021).

Here is an in-depth analysis on the reading performance of Grade 7 students after they were immersed in a reading laboratory:

The reading laboratory approach was found to significantly improve the reading performance of Grade 7 students, particularly in the areas of phonics and decoding, vocabulary, and reading comprehension.

The results showed statistically significant improvements in the students' reading abilities. On phonics and decoding, the students demonstrated better ability to recognize and manipulate sounds and letters after the reading laboratory program.

In vocabulary, the students exhibited an increased understanding and application of synonyms, antonyms, idiomatic expressions, and using context clues to determine word meanings.

Most importantly, the students' reading comprehension levels increased substantially. They were better able to extract meaning, make inferences, and integrate new information from the texts they read.

The reading laboratory approach was effective because it provided students with extensive exposure to a wide variety of high-quality reading materials, which is crucial for developing strong reading skills. The program also incorporated explicit instruction and scaffolding from teachers to support the students' learning.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that a well-designed reading laboratory can be a highly valuable supplementary program to improve the reading performance of struggling Grade 7 students across key competencies. Implementing such an approach can be an important initiative to boost overall reading development in schools.

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3.3 Test of Significant Difference in Reading Performance Before and After Immersion in Reading Laboratory.

Table 3

Test of Significant Difference

	Mean	df	T-value	T-Critical	Decision	Interpretation
Pretest	5.4	9	12.074	0.00001	Reject the Null Hypothesis	Significant
Posttest	11.7					

Data on the table above reveals the test of significant difference between the pretest and posttest of grade 7 in Filipino. Specifically, it can be gleaned from the table that the learners' posted 5.40 and 11.70 mean score during the pretest and posttest respectively. The t computed value of 12.074 is higher than the t- critical value of 2.262 at a 0.05 level of significance with degrees of freedom 9. With that, the null hypothesis is rejected. This only means that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest. Also, the result exemplified that the post test scores of the students immersed in the reading laboratory or the experimental group is significantly performing compared to pre immersion in reading laboratory.

Related study on the effectiveness of remedial reading to struggling readers of Grade 7 students at Bolo Norte High School, conducted by Leonard Ivan B. Abergos et al., found a significant difference in the reading comprehension level of respondents before and after the remedial reading program. The study used descriptive and documentary methods to analyze the pre-test and post-test results of 120 Grade-7 students who were identified as struggling readers based on their performance on the standardized reading assessment administered by the school. The results showed that the reading comprehension level of the respondents on the pre-test was 6.68, interpreted as "Emerging." After the first five months of implementation, the post-test result was 11.10, interpreted as "Developing." A paired T-test was conducted to determine the significance of this improvement, and the t-value of -9.21 and the associated p-value of 0.000 suggest a significant difference between the pre and post-test scores. This indicates that remedial reading is effective in improving reading comprehension. This study is related to the significant difference in reading performance of Grade 7 students before and after their immersion on reading laboratory, as it demonstrates the effectiveness of remedial reading in improving reading comprehension.

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The study found a statistically significant difference between the pretest and posttest reading comprehension levels. This demonstrates that reading laboratory immersion was effective in improving the reading performance of the Grade 7 students.

3.4 Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of the Reading Laboratory

The implementation of reading laboratories in educational settings can be a complex and challenging process. Several issues can arise during the design and implementation of such programs, which can impact their effectiveness in improving reading skills.

Implementing reading laboratories can be a daunting task, particularly when faced with the diverse needs and abilities of students. Several challenges can hinder the success of these programs, including:

- **Resource Constraints** – Setting up a well-equipped reading Laboratory requires financial resources to purchase books, technology, instructional materials, and other necessary resources. Limited funding may pose a challenge in creating an effective and engaging reading environment.
- **Space Limitations** – Adequate space is crucial for a reading laboratory to accommodate multiple students and provide a comfortable reading environment. Limited space can restrict the number of students who can access the laboratory simultaneously or limit the availability of diverse reading materials
- **Staffing and Expertise** – A reading laboratory requires trained staff who are knowledgeable about reading instruction and can effectively support struggling readers. Finding qualified personnel and ensuring ongoing professional development can be a challenge.
- **Scheduling and Time Constraints** – Coordinating schedules to ensure that students have regular access to the reading laboratory can be challenging, especially in schools with limited time allocated for reading instruction. Balancing other academic subjects and extracurricular activities can also impact the availability of students for reading laboratory sessions.
- **Assessment and Progress Monitoring** – Assessing and monitoring the progress of students in a reading laboratory can be challenging. Implementing appropriate assessment tools and tracking individual student growth can require careful planning and coordination.

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3.5 Proposed Action Plan

Areas of Concern	Strategy	Activity	Means of Verification
Resource Constraints	<p>-Prioritize essential resources based on student needs and budget constraints.</p> <p>-Seek external funding through grants, sponsorships, or community partnerships to supplement the available resources.</p>	Community Partnership	<p>Documentation</p> <p>Monitoring Tool</p> <p>Accomplishment Report</p>
Space Limitations	Maximize the available space by arranging flexible seating, utilizing vertical storage, and creating cozy reading corners.	MaxiSpace	Photo Documentation
Staffing and Expertise	Provide professional development opportunities for existing staff to enhance their knowledge and skills in reading instruction.	PPDO (Provide Professional Development Opportunities)	Certificate of Participation in Seminars/Trainings on reading
Scheduling and Time Constraints	<p>-Implement a rotating schedule where different groups of students have access to the reading laboratory on specific days or weeks.</p> <p>-Collaborate with classroom teachers to integrate reading laboratory activities into the regular curriculum.</p>	Provide a copy of the schedule to all teachers.	<p>Documentation</p> <p>Monitoring tool</p> <p>Accomplishment Report</p>
Assessment and Progress Monitoring	Implement a comprehensive assessment plan that includes pre-and post- assessments to track individual student progress.	CAP (Comprehensive Assessment Plan)	Progress Report

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CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions and recommendations are critical components of a research report that summarize the key findings and provide guidance for future actions or research.

Conclusions are interpretations of the research findings that answer the original research questions or hypotheses. This highlight the most important results and explain their significance in the context of the study. Conclusions should be based on the evidence presented in the report and should take into account any limitations of the research.

Recommendations are specific actions or suggestions for future research or real-world applications based on the conclusions. They provide guidance for stakeholders on how to use the research findings. Recommendations should be practical, feasible, and clearly linked to the conclusions.

Conclusion

Based from the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. All of the grade 7 learners were beginners in reading performance before the immersion Reading Laboratory.
2. All of the Grade 7 learners were developing in reading performance after the immersion Reading Laboratory.
3. There is a significant difference between the pretest and post test in reading
4. Resource Constraints, Space Limitations, Staffing and Expertise, Scheduling and Time Constraints and Assesment and Progress monitoring were the challenges encountered in the implementation of Reading Laboratory.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions made, the following recommendations were offered:

1. Implement a Structured Phonics Program – design and implement a structured phonics program within the reading laboratory to explicitly teach phonemic awareness, phonics, and decoding skills.
2. Continue Targeted Instruction – maintain the implementation of targeted instruction and interventions within the reading laboratory to further support the development of the students' reading skills.
3. Sustain and improve the Reading Laboratory – ensure the sustained implementation and improvement of the reading laboratory program. Continually evaluate the program's effectiveness, collect feedback from students and staff, and make necessary adjustents to enhance its outcome.
4. Prioritize essential resources based on student needs and budget constraints and seek external funding through grnats sponsorships, or community partnerships to supplement the available resources.

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